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- Spotlight on Emerging Writers
- Poetry
- Short Stories
- Essays
- Creative Corner
- Others

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“YOU'RE A MOTHER!”

Once child, ideas wide
Cannot hide excitement inside
Take on life, away from life

Bear the child, womb inside
Happy and wild, sore aside
Mother bear me life

Sages whispered, child to disown
Start to finish never yours
Explain cannot fathom

Child expense more than life
Why oh why, sages why?
I lost life for life
Mother dies for life from womb
Now she is tomb
Losing life for life
Never owns.

